

EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF CNT/POLYMER COMPOSITES USING A MODIFIED MSM METHOD COMBINED WITH A COHESIVE LAW FOR INTERFACES

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1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been used as ideal reinforcements to composites due to their superior mechanical properties. Tension and compression simulations based on both discrete and continuous models have been used to represent mechanical behaviors of the CNT reinforced composites. But in the interface between the CNTs and the matrix, only weak van der Waals (vdW) forces rather than strong bonds exist. Therefore, precisely characterize the mechanics in nano-based composites at multiscale including the vdW interactions is still a formidable challenge.

He et al. [1] provided explicit formulas for the vdW interaction between any two layers of a multi-walled CNT and established an efficient algorithm for the buckling analysis of multi-walled CNTs. Based on the vdW forces for interfaces between the CNTs and the matrix, Lu et al. [2] developed a cohesive zone model which could provide the link between the nanoscale vdW forces and macroscopic mechanical properties of composite materials. A molecular structural mechanics (MSM) approach has been developed for modeling CNTs which provide an approach to investigate the molecular structures using continuum models [3].

In this paper, a uniaxial micro-mechanical model of CNT/polymer composite is established based on a cohesive law for interfaces between CNTs and polymers due to van der Waals interactions. Effective stress-strain relations of CNT/polymer composites are derived by combining the microscopic model which can provide vdW forces to the continuum models and a modified

MSM method which can characterize nonlinear stress-strain relations of CNTs.

2 Methodology

2.1 Cohesive law for CNT/polymer interface

The vdW interactions are usually represented by the Lennard-Jones 6–12 potential as

$$V(r) = 4\varepsilon \left(\frac{\sigma^{12}}{r^{12}} - \frac{\sigma^6}{r^6} \right) \quad (1)$$

where V is the energy between a pair of atoms of distance r , and ε is the bond energy at the equilibrium distance. For a pair of carbon atoms, the bond energy and equilibrium distance are $\varepsilon_{C-C} = 0.002390$ eV and $\sigma_{C-C} = 0.3415$ nm. For a carbon atom and a $-CH_2-$ unit in polymer, $\varepsilon_{C-CH_2} = 0.004656$ eV and $\sigma_{C-CH_2} = 0.3825$ nm [2].

The schematic model of a MWCNT/polymer is illustrated in Fig.1. The radii of the CNT walls are denoted by R_i , the spacing between the outermost CNT wall and the polymer surface is denoted by h . The cohesive energy among all CNTs is

$$\Phi_{\text{CNT-CNT}} = 2\pi^2 \rho_C^2 \varepsilon_{C-C} \sigma_{C-C}^2 \times \sum_{1 \leq i \leq j \leq n} \left[\frac{2\sigma_{C-C}^{10}}{5(R_i - R_j)h^{10}} - \frac{\sigma_{C-C}^4}{(R_i - R_j)h^4} \right] \cdot (R_i + R_j) \quad (i < j) \quad (2)$$

And the cohesive energy between polymer and all CNTs is

$$\Phi_{\text{CNT-polymer}} = \frac{2\pi^2}{3} \rho_{\text{CH}_2} \rho_c \varepsilon_{\text{C-CH}_2} \sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^3 \times \sum_{1 \leq i \leq n} \left\{ 2R_i \left[\frac{2\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^9}{15(R_i - R_i + h)h^9} - \frac{\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^3}{(R_i - R_i + h)^3} \right] + \frac{3}{2} \sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2} \left[\frac{\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^8}{10(R_i - R_i + h)^8} - \frac{\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^2}{(R_i - R_i + h)^2} \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

Fig.1 A schematic diagram of CNT in a polymer

For the opening displacement ν_1 between the outermost CNT and polymer beyond the equilibrium distance h with $h + \nu_1$. The derivative of total cohesive energy with respect to ν_1 gives the tensile cohesive stress. For a SWCNT and polymer, the cohesive stress is given by

$$\sigma^{\text{int}} = -2\pi\rho_{\text{CH}_2} \rho_c \varepsilon_{\text{C-CH}_2} \sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^2 \left(1 + \frac{\nu_1}{2R + 0.858\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}} \right) \times \left[\frac{2\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^{10}}{5(0.858\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2} + \nu_1)^{10}} - \frac{\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^4}{(0.858\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2} + \nu_1)^4} \right] \quad (4)$$

where the average area $\pi(2R_1 + 0.858\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2})$ between the outermost CNT wall and polymer is used in the cohesive stress calculation. For a MWCNT/polymer, the cohesive stress is

$$\sigma_{\text{cohesive}} = -2\pi\rho_{\text{CH}_2} \rho_c \varepsilon_{\text{C-CH}_2} \sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^2 \times \sum_{1 \leq i \leq n} \left[1 + \frac{\nu_1 - (i-1)\sigma_{\text{C-C}}}{2R_1 + 0.858\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}} \right] \times \left[\frac{2\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^{10}}{5[0.858\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2} + (i-1)\sigma_{\text{C-C}} + \nu_1]^{10}} - \frac{\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2}^4}{[0.858\sigma_{\text{C-CH}_2} + (i-1)\sigma_{\text{C-C}} + \nu_1]^4} \right] \quad (5)$$

2.2 Elastic mechanical solution of CNTs /polymer composite

To study the macroscopic stress-strain behaviors of CNT reinforced polymer composites, a uniaxial CNT/polymer model, schematically shown in Fig. 2, is considered. The model contains a CNT of outermost radius R_c , embedded in a coaxial hollow cylindrical matrix of inner radius r_m outer radius R_m , in where the value of R_m is determined by the volume fraction f of the CNT. In the nonlinear uniaxial model for CNT reinforced composites, the CNT and the surrounding matrix are envisaged as isotropic cylinder shells submitted to axial load and radial pressure, cohesive stress σ^{int} , between the outermost CNT wall and the polymer as plotted in Fig.2. Hence, as a continuum model, the elastic mechanical solutions for the two components of the composite can be obtained by investigating them separately.

We first consider the elastic mechanical solution for the polymer of inside radius r_m and outside radius R_m , only radial stress σ^{int} due to normal opening displacement between the outermost CNT wall and the inside wall of the polymer are exerted on it (Fig.2a). According to the tensile mechanics, the radial stress and circumferential stress of the polymer can be obtained as,

$$\sigma_r^m = -\frac{R_m^2/r^2 - 1}{R_m^2/r_m^2 - 1} \sigma^{\text{int}} \quad (6a)$$

$$\sigma_\theta^m = \frac{R_m^2/r^2 + 1}{R_m^2/r_m^2 - 1} \sigma^{\text{int}} \quad (6b)$$

The axial strain ε_z^m of the matrix leads to its radial displacement of the inside wall as

$$\nu_r^m = \frac{1}{E^m} \left[-(1 + \mu^m) \frac{A^m}{r} + 2(1 - \mu^m) C^m r \right] - \mu^m \varepsilon_z^m r \quad (7)$$

where $A^m = -\frac{(r^m)^2 (R^m)^2}{(R^m)^2 - (r^m)^2} \sigma^{\text{int}}$, $2C^m = \frac{(r^m)^2}{(R^m)^2 - (r^m)^2} \sigma^{\text{int}}$.

For the CNT of an innermost radius r_c and a outermost radius R_c bearing the same radial stress σ^{int} as introduced above (Fig.2b), similar elastic mechanics solution can be derived.

The radial stress and circumferential stress of the CNT are

$$\sigma_r^c = -\frac{1 - r_c^2/r^2}{1 - r_c^2/R_c^2} \sigma^{\text{int}} \quad (8a)$$

$$\sigma_r^c = -\frac{1 + r_c^2/r^2}{1 - r_c^2/R_c^2} \sigma^{\text{int}} \quad (8b)$$

And the same axial strain ε_z^m gives rise to radial displacement of the outermost wall of the CNT as

$$\nu_r^c = \frac{1}{E^c} \left[-(1 + \mu^c) \frac{A^c}{r} + 2(1 - \mu^c) C^c r \right] - \mu^c \varepsilon_z^c r \quad (9)$$

where $A^c = \frac{(r^c)^2 (R^c)^2}{(R^c)^2 - (r^c)^2} \sigma^{\text{int}}$, $2C^c = -\frac{(R^c)^2}{(R^c)^2 - (r^c)^2} \sigma^{\text{int}}$.

Fig.2 Stress diagram of illustration of the CNT/polymer model

Hence, as the composite undergoing a uniform axial strain, a normal opening displacement between the outermost wall of the CNT and the polymer can be given as

$$\begin{aligned} \nu &= \nu_r^m \Big|_{r=r^m} + \nu_r^c \Big|_{r=R^c} \\ &= \frac{1}{E^m} \left[-(1 + \mu^m) \frac{A^m}{r^m} + 2(1 - \mu^m) C^m r^m \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{E^c} \left[-(1 + \mu^c) \frac{A^c}{R^c} + 2(1 - \mu^c) C^c R^c \right] - (\mu^m r^m - \mu^c R^c) \bar{\varepsilon} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

2.3 Macroscopic tensile stress-strain relations of the CNT/polymer composite

For a nanocomposite under uniaxial loading, the dependence of its longitudinal elastic stress on the CNT volume fraction f can be estimated by the rule of mixtures. The averaged uniaxial elastic stress, $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}$, of the composite cell with long CNT under a uniform strain conditions $\varepsilon_{zz}^c = \varepsilon_{zz}^m = \bar{\varepsilon}$ is

$$\bar{\sigma}_{zz} = f \sigma_{zz}^c + (1 - f) \sigma_{zz}^m \quad (11)$$

where σ_{zz}^m and σ_{zz}^c are uniaxial stress of the CNT and the polymer, separately. Since the CNT and the surrounding matrix are viewed as isotropic materials, the uniaxial strain ε_{zz}^c and ε_{zz}^m of the CNT and the matrix can be expressed by the stress components based on Hooker's law as,

$$\varepsilon_{zz}^c = \bar{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{E^c} \left[\sigma_{zz}^c - \mu^c (\sigma_{rr}^c + \sigma_{\theta\theta}^c) \right] \quad (12a)$$

$$\varepsilon_{zz}^m = \bar{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{E^m} \left[\sigma_{zz}^m - \mu^m (\sigma_{rr}^m + \sigma_{\theta\theta}^m) \right] \quad (12b)$$

where E^c and E^m denote Young's modulus of the CNT and polymer, μ^c and μ^m indicate Poisson's ratio of the CNT and the polymer, and σ_{rr}^c , $\sigma_{\theta\theta}^c$, σ_{rr}^m and $\sigma_{\theta\theta}^m$ are radial and circumferential stress components of the CNT and the polymer.

Therefore, the axial stress of the CNT and the polymer can be expressed as

$$\sigma_{zz}^c = E^c \bar{\varepsilon} + \mu^c (\sigma_{rr}^c + \sigma_{\theta\theta}^c) \quad (13a)$$

$$\sigma_{zz}^m = E^m \bar{\varepsilon} + \mu^m (\sigma_{rr}^m + \sigma_{\theta\theta}^m) \quad (13b)$$

Substrate Eq. (3a) and (3b) to (1) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_{zz} &= f \sigma_{zz}^c + (1 - f) \sigma_{zz}^m \\ &= f \left[E^c \bar{\varepsilon} + \mu^c (\sigma_{rr}^c + \sigma_{\theta\theta}^c) \right] + (1 - f) \left[E^m \bar{\varepsilon} + \mu^m (\sigma_{rr}^m + \sigma_{\theta\theta}^m) \right] \\ &= [f E^c + (1 - f) E^m] \bar{\varepsilon} \\ &\quad + [f \mu^c (\sigma_{rr}^c + \sigma_{\theta\theta}^c) + (1 - f) \mu^m (\sigma_{rr}^m + \sigma_{\theta\theta}^m)] \end{aligned}$$

(14)

Replace the radial and circumferential components of stress by cohesive stress, one can obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\sigma}_{zz} &= f\sigma_{zz}^c + (1-f)\sigma_{zz}^m \\ &= f\left[E^c\bar{\varepsilon} + \mu^c(\sigma_{rr}^c + \sigma_{\theta\theta}^c)\right] + (1-f)\left[E^m\bar{\varepsilon} + \mu^m(\sigma_{rr}^m + \sigma_{\theta\theta}^m)\right] \\ &= [fE^c + (1-f)E^m]\bar{\varepsilon} + \left[\frac{-2f\mu^c}{1-r_c^2/R_c^2} + \frac{2(1-f)\mu^m}{R_m^2/r_m^2-1}\right]\sigma^{\text{int}}\end{aligned}\quad (15)$$

In the right-hand side, the second term is a correction term to the rule of mixture which will vanish when the cohesive stress disappears.

2.4 The modified MSM method

For the covalent bonds of MCNTs, in the original MSM method [3], the total steric potential energy is a sum of energies due to bond stretch interaction, bond angle bending and dihedral angle torsion:

$$U = \sum U_r + \sum U_\theta + \sum U_\phi \quad (16)$$

For sake of simplicity and convenience, the simplest harmonic forms are adopted and the dihedral angle torsion and the improper torsion are merged into a single equivalent term, i.e.,

$$U_r = \frac{1}{2}k_r(\Delta r)^2 \quad (17)$$

where the stretch force constant value is chosen based upon the experience with graphite sheets: $k_r = 983 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} \text{ \AA}^{-2}$. The symbols Δr represents the bond stretching increment. However, the universal force field describes the bond stretch interaction can also as the Morse function [4]:

$$E_r = D[e^{-\alpha(r-r_0)} - 1]^2 \quad (18)$$

where the dissociation energy D is set to 124 kcal/mol and $\alpha = [k_r / 2D]^{1/2} = 1.9448 \times 10^{10} / \text{m}$.

The Morse function is a more accurate description since it implicitly includes anharmonic terms near equilibrium (r_0) and leads to a finite energy (D_r) for breaking bonds. By making E_r equivalent to U_r , the bond stretching force constant k_r is turned to a variable with the bond stretching increment as

$$k_r = \frac{D[e^{-\alpha(r-r_0)} - 1]^2}{(r-r_0)^2} \quad (19)$$

Therefore, nonlinear tensile stress-strain response of the CNTs can be obtained by using the modified MSM approach.

3 Discussion

Effective stress-strain relations of CNT/polymer composites are derived by combining molecular structure mechanics (MSM) and the microscopic model proposed above. Effect of volume fraction and the wall number of the CNTs on the effective properties of the corresponding CNT reinforced polymer composites are discussed here.

Fig.3 Effective stress-strain curves of SWCNT/polymer with and without vdW interactions

Fig.4 Effective stress-strain curves of
MWCNT/polymer with and without vdW
interactions

As shown in Fig.3, effective stress-strain curves of SWCNT/polymer composites with and without consideration of the vdW forces are illustrated. It is shown that the effective stress is higher when the vdW interactions are taken into account and the vdW forces play a more important role in a composite with a higher volume fraction of CNT. What's more, as illustrated in Fig.4, the effective stress is much improved as the CNT Waals number increases but the effect of the vdW forces is slight.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, a microscopic uniaxial shell model of CNT/polymer composite is established and a multi-scale analysis is carried out by taking vdW interactions into account. Effective stress-strain relations of CNT/polymer composites are derived by combining molecular structure mechanics (MSM) and the microscopic model which provides vdW forces to the continuum models. The simulation results indicated that the vdW forces can be efficiently involved in the continuum models and play an important role in the investigation of stress-strain relations of the CNT/polymer.

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